

Technology and Higher Education: What Works and what is the Future?

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Abstract: Technology has created many new educational models. This research presents a review of the literature on technology-assisted educational models, proposes new models based on existing research, and surveys over 5,000 college students, instructors, and business professionals regarding which model(s) did or could serve them best. Results show that students still prefer traditional technologies for their educational experience, and do not want that experience to become entirely online. However, there is evidence that online, virtual and interactive videos are appreciated for Content Delivery, online work for questions, homework, and course materials is appreciated for Content Practice, and online discussion boards and interaction are appreciated for Content Discussion.

Keywords: Empirical, Higher Education, Survey Research, Technology

I. INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Rapid advancements in technology continue to transform the world we live in, and higher education is no exception (Lytras et al., 2018). Bower & Christensen (1995) coined the term “disruptive technologies”, and many prognosticators felt certain that the traditional method of education was in jeopardy. Twenty-five years later, the lecture method still survives and dominates the majority of colleges and universities across the world (Martin 2012; Wurdinger & Carlson, 2009). While the traditional lecture method endures, technology is being experimented with, injected into, and utilized at an increasing rate (Concannon et al., 2005; Downing et al., 2014; Spring & Graham, 2017). Newer educational models using technology have proven to be more efficient (Barkley, 2009; Spring & Graham, 2017), more effective (Barkley, 2009; Downing et al., 2014; Tallent-Runnels et al., 2006; Turner & Carriveau, 2010), and more profitable (Christensen & Eyring, 2011). Moving to a completely online model threatened to truly disrupt the higher education community. But the excitement ballooned and then receded, with the juggernaut of the online industry, the University of Phoenix, seeing its enrollments decline from 460,000 in 2010 to 212,000 in 2016 (Beaver, 2017). But the disruption has occurred, and even the most techno-phobic observers acknowledge that technology will be heavily used in the learning processes of the future (Lytras et al., 2018).

Valid questions for all involved include “How much technology should be used, and in what manner, in higher education? Which model(s) is best?” (Larreamendy-Joerns & Leinhardt, 2006; Swaner, 2012). Administrators and educators in colleges and universities need guidelines concerning what works, what does not, and where the future may lead regarding technology usage in the higher education learning experience. This paper will review the literature on technology-assisted educational models, propose new models based on existing research, and survey over 5,000 former college students, college instructors, and business professionals regarding which model(s) did or could serve them best. Turner & Carriveau (2010) explain that the learning experience will be best in a course that consists of the following three components: Content Delivery, Content Practice, and Content Discussion and Experience. Technology can be used in any of these components, and this research will explore both the use (which component and what type) and the amount (how much of that component is delivered using technology).

Content Delivery

Content Delivery is how course topics are communicated to students, and traditional technologies include lectures, overhead projection, PowerPoint, and textbooks (Bando et al., 2017; Tseng & Walsh, 2016). Any other technology used would be “non-traditional” (MacDonald & Thompson, 2005). Mobile, e-learning, tablets and social media tools have

led the way in content delivery in the non-traditional sphere (El-Hussein & Cronje, 2010; Hung & Yuen, 2010; Reychav & Wu, 2015; Wagner, Hassanein & Head, 2008). However, increasingly innovative new methods continue to emerge. Shirazi & Behzadan (2015) describe how Augmented Reality (AR) can be used as a content delivery method to improve student performance. Students ranked the effectiveness of the AR tool very highly and praised its potential to transform traditional teaching methods. Lee et al. (2017) discuss how virtual reality (using Google Cardboard) as a content delivery system in business classrooms has led to higher student ratings of their enjoyment and interest in the content.

Content Practice

Content Practice is how students personally engage with and experience the course content, and includes things like assignments, and classroom and outside of classroom exercises. Traditional technology is paper/pencil/computer-based tasks and overhead projection instructor-led tasks (Sambell et al., 2017; Turner & Carriveau, 2010). Any other technology used would be "non-traditional". Studies have shown that the connected students of today can greatly increase their practice with the course content if informal learning, through social media platforms, chat groups, and discussion boards, is encouraged and made available either by the instructor or the students themselves (Lai & Smith, 2018).

Content Discussion

Content Discussion is the process of students asking questions, making comments, and getting answers about course content. Traditional technology is in-person classroom interaction with the instructor (hand-raising, etc.) and other students, email with the instructor and other students, and instructor-provided discussion boards. Any other technology used would be "non-traditional". Shirazi & Behzadan (2015) detail how students who used AR spent more time on collaboration, communication, and exchanging ideas as compared to students who used traditional methods of receiving content.

II. RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND HYPOTHESES

The "What type of technology is being used?" dimension will be Boolean, being either "Traditional" or "Non-Traditional". "Traditional" technology for content delivery would be lectures or PowerPoint slides, for example, while "Non-Traditional" would basically be anything else, including examples like student-lead virtual group lessons, etc. "Non-Traditional" methods of technology usage are of significant interest for this research, and since this is a wide-ranging and nebulous group, open-ended feedback will be used to gather best practices. For the question "How much of that component is delivered using technology?", again the initial dimensions will be Boolean, dividing at 50%. The initial research hypotheses will be that a component where technology is used for more than 50% of its delivery will have a learning experience perceived to be at least as good as a component where technology is used for 50% or less of the delivery. Degree and impact of how technology is being used and how much technology is being used was explored in a pilot study, and hypotheses were adjusted accordingly. Similarly, comparisons were made across technology usage in components (e.g., Does using more technology for content delivery than content practice produce a better learning experience?). Table 1 shows how the research hypotheses will be initially organized, and the enumeration of the hypotheses follows.

Table 1. Initial Organization of Research Hypotheses

Technology Used	Technology Used for: Content Delivery	Technology Used for: Content Practice	Technology Used for: Content Discussion and Experience
Traditional	(e.g., Lectures, PowerPoint slides) 50%?	(e.g., paper/pencil/computer-based tasks and overhead projection instructor-led tasks) 50%?	(e.g., in-person classroom interaction with the instructor (hand-raising, etc.) and other students, email) 50%?
Non-Traditional	50%?	50%?	50%?

The following research hypotheses will be tested:

Technology and Higher Education: What Works and What is the Future?

- H1: A course where traditional technology is used for more than 50% of the content delivery will have a learning experience perceived to be at least as good as a course where traditional technology is used for 50% or less of the content delivery.
- H2: A course where traditional technology is used for more than 50% of the content practice will have a learning experience perceived to be at least as good as a course where traditional technology is used for 50% or less of the content practice.
- H3: A course where traditional technology is used for more than 50% of the content discussion and experience will have a learning experience perceived to be at least as good as a course where traditional technology is used for 50% or less of the content discussion and experience.
- H4: A course where non-traditional technology is used for more than 50% of the content delivery will have a learning experience perceived to be at least as good as a course where non-traditional technology is used for 50% or less of the content delivery. [Important exploration: What is the non-traditional technology, and how is it used?]
- H5: A course where non-traditional technology is used for more than 50% of the content practice will have a learning experience perceived to be at least as good as a course where non-traditional technology is used for 50% or less of the content practice. [Important exploration: What is the non-traditional technology, how is it used, and how much better does it make the experience?]
- H6: A course where non-traditional technology is used for more than 50% of the content discussion and experience will have a learning experience perceived to be at least as good as a course where non-traditional technology is used for 50% or less of the content discussion and experience. [Important exploration: What is the non-traditional technology, how is it used, and how much better does it make the experience?]
- H7: A fully online course provides a learning experience perceived to be at least as good as a hybrid or fully face-to-face course.

III. METHODOLOGY

One method to determine best practices is to ask a large number of people who have had experience in that area, also called “crowdsourcing” (Harward & Finley, 2012; Herrington et al., 2003). Studies have shown that crowdsourcing can lead to some of the most meaningful answers to difficult questions (Tucci et al., 2018), and crowdsourcing will be used as the methodology for this research. In particular, a vast, longitudinal cross-section of students, instructors and business professionals numbering over 5,000 and who have taken and/or taught at least one business class, was surveyed regarding questions about technology usage in higher education. The survey was distributed via email, and anonymously taken online. The majority of the questions were statements with Likert-scale responses, but there were also opportunities for open-ended responses. Text analysis, using word clouds, was used to analyze the open-ended responses, given the volume of responses.

To measure and determine which uses of technology are “best” or “effective”, the seminal work “Assessing the Impact of Technology in Teaching and Learning”, from the University of Michigan (Johnston & Baker, 2002), was used as the basis for survey construction. The evaluation areas of Audience/Stakeholder Group, Communication, Consequences, and Improvement were used to create the content of the survey questions, with the goal being the assessment of the effectiveness of the technology usage models. Given that the survey was created for this research, reliability of constructs was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha for scales with three or more items and correlation analysis for scales with two items. Cronbach's Alpha results above .6 are considered to demonstrate reliability of a construct, as well as correlation significance at the .01 level (Hair, et al., 2005), and these levels were obtained.

IV. DATA COLLECTION, ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A seven-point Likert-scale was used for each statement seeking agreement or disagreement in the survey administered to the students. Answers ranged from “Strongly Agree” (numeric value 1) to “Strongly Disagree” (numeric value 7). One hundred and sixty-one students responded out of 5,190 given the opportunity (response rate = $161/5190 = 3.1\%$). The full survey instrument appears in the Appendix. The mean responses to each question, for each hypothesis, along with the t-test results, appear in Table 1.

Table 1. Hypotheses, Means, and Results

	Question	H ₀	Mean	Result
H1	I believe courses where traditional technology (e.g., lectures, overhead projection, PowerPoint, textbooks) is used for more than 50% of the content delivery will have a learning experience at least as good as courses where traditional technology is used for 50% or less of the content delivery.	$\mu > 3$	2.69	t = -2.1419, df = 160, p-value = 0.01686 Reject H ₀ true mean is less than or equal to 3
H2	I believe courses where traditional technology (paper/pencil/computer-based tasks and overhead projection instructor-led tasks) is used for more than 50% of the content practice will have a learning experience at least as good as courses where traditional technology is used for 50% or less of the content practice.	$\mu > 3$	2.78	t = -1.8761, df = 159, p-value = 0.03124 Reject H ₀ true mean is less than or equal to 3
H3	I believe courses where traditional technology (e.g., in-person classroom interaction with the instructor (hand-raising, etc.) and other students, email with the instructor and other students, and instructor-provided discussion boards) is used for more than 50% of the content discussion will have a learning experience at least as good as courses where traditional technology is used for 50% or less of the content discussion.	$\mu > 3$	2.61	t = -3.0506, df = 156, p-value = 0.001342 Reject H ₀ true mean is less than or equal to 3
H4	I believe courses where non-traditional technology (anything OTHER than lectures, overhead projection, PowerPoint, and textbooks) is used for more than 50% of the content delivery will have a learning experience at least as good as courses where non-traditional technology is used for 50% or less of the content delivery.	$\mu > 3$	3.23	t = 1.7945, df = 160, p-value = 0.9627 Accept H ₀ true mean is greater than 3
H5	I believe courses where non-traditional technology (anything OTHER than paper/pencil/computer-based tasks and overhead projection instructor-led tasks) is used for more than 50% of the content practice will have a learning experience at least as good as courses where non-traditional technology is used for 50% or less of the content practice.	$\mu > 3$	3.12	t = 0.95574, df = 159, p-value = 0.8297 Accept H ₀ true mean is greater than 3
H6	I believe courses where non-traditional technology (anything OTHER than in-person classroom interaction with the instructor (hand-raising, etc.) and other students, email with the instructor and other students, and instructor-provided discussion boards) is used for more than 50% of the content discussion will have a learning experience at least as good as courses where non-traditional technology is used for 50% or less of the content discussion.	$\mu > 3$	3.63	t = 4.6995, df = 157, p-value = 1 Accept H ₀ true mean is greater than 3
H7	I believe a fully online course provides a learning experience at least as good as a hybrid or fully face-to-face course.	$\mu > 3$	3.94	t = 6.2666, df = 159, p-value = 1 Accept H ₀ true mean is greater than 3

What

How

Figure 2. H5: Important exploration: What is the non-traditional technology, and how is it used? Word Clouds for WHAT and HOW non-traditional technology should be used for Content Practice

What

How

Figure 3. H6: Important exploration: What is the non-traditional technology, and how is it used? Word Clouds for WHAT and HOW non-traditional technology should be used for Content Discussion

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

As shown in Table 1, the testing was done against a mean of 3, which is “Somewhat Agree” with 1 being “Strongly Agree”, with H0 being $\mu > 3$, meaning H0 was that students were neutral or disagreed with the statement. The first three statements, relating to H1-H3, had H0 rejected, meaning students agreed with the statements. Each of these statements claimed that courses where traditional technology was used for more than 50% of Content Delivery, Content Practice, and Content Discussion, respectively, would have learning experiences at least as good as courses where traditional technology was used for 50% or less. This is a strong statement for the continued perceived value of

traditional methods. It is very difficult to break this culture. Valid or not, the students' perceptions is that heavy (more than 50%) use of traditional methods of education will produce superior learning experiences. Similarly, the next three statements, relating to H4-H6, had H0 accepted, meaning students disagreed with the statements. Each of these statements claimed that courses where non-traditional technology was used for more than 50% of Content Delivery, Content Practice, and Content Discussion, respectively, would have learning experiences at least as good as courses where non-traditional technology was used for 50% or less. Again here, the students favor traditional methods, and are wary of injecting too much (more than 50%) non-traditional technology into their learning experiences. Having said that, the averages hovered around 3 (as shown in Table 1), and there were many positive reactions regarding non-traditional technology. Because of this, word clouds were used to gain an understanding of both How and What the students thought could be done using non-traditional technology in the areas of Content Delivery, Content Practice, and Content Discussion. The R script used to create the word clouds is shown in Table 2, and the results are shown in Figures 1, 2 and 3.

While the word clouds do not carry the statistical validity of the hypothesis tests, they nonetheless provide anecdotal evidence for educators going forward. Looking at Figure 1, there is evidence that online, virtual and interactive videos are preferred for Content Delivery. Figure 2 suggests that online work for questions, homework, and course materials is preferred for Content Practice. And finally, Figure 3 lends credence to this online model, with online discussion boards and interaction as the primary possible methods for Content Discussion. Importantly, hypothesis testing of H7 demonstrated that students disagreed with the statement "I believe a fully online course provides a learning experience at least as good as a hybrid or fully face-to-face course", so the online presence is useful but should not completely dominate.

These results are important for administrators and educators going forward. However, this is not a panacea; more work needs to be done. In particular, as technologies continue to emerge and threaten traditional methods, they need to be studied, analyzed and discussed. It is entirely likely that the change that is occurring toward advanced technologies is an incremental one, and could be in the early stages. Also, a larger sample size, spanning multiple institutions and class types, would be helpful.

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Technology and Higher Education: What Works and What is the Future?

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APPENDIX – SURVEY INSTRUMENT

Technology and Higher Education: What Works and What is the Future?

Thank you for participating in this research study. This study focuses on your opinion of how effective traditional ("old school", "normal") technology and non-traditional ("newer", "cutting edge") technology is in three areas of education: Content Delivery, Content Practice, and Content Discussion. If you believe a non-traditional technology has promise in these areas, you are asked to list that technology and how it could be used.

Section 1: Demographics

1. I give my permission for Dr. Downing to use my survey responses for research purposes.

Yes

No

2. What is your age?

Select your answer

3. How many total years of full-time higher education coursework have you completed?

Select your answer

4. How many courses have you taken where at least 50% of the course delivery was online?

Select your answer

5. How many 100% online courses have you taken?

Select your answer

Next

Technology and Higher Education: What Works and What is the Future?

Section 2: Technology in Higher Education: Content Delivery

This section asks you to think about traditional versus non-traditional technology in CONTENT DELIVERY. Content Delivery is how course topics are communicated to students, and traditional technologies include lectures, overhead projection, PowerPoint, and textbooks. Any other technology used would be "non-traditional".

6. Please rate your agreement or disagreement with the following statement:

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Somewhat Agree	Neutral	Somewhat Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I believe courses where traditional technology (e.g., lectures, overhead projection, PowerPoint, textbooks) is used for more than 50% of the content delivery will have a learning experience at least as good as courses where traditional technology is used for 50% or less of the content delivery.	<input type="radio"/>						

7. Please rate your agreement or disagreement with the following statement:

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Somewhat Agree	Neutral	Somewhat Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I believe courses where non-traditional technology (anything OTHER than lectures, overhead projection, PowerPoint, and textbooks) is used for more than 50% of the content delivery will have a learning experience at least as good as courses where non-traditional technology is used for 50% or less of the content delivery.	<input type="radio"/>						

8. What is the non-traditional technology that you are referring to in your answer to Question #7?

9. How should this non-traditional technology (your answer from Question #8) be used for content delivery?

10. On a scale of 1-10, 10 being the most, how much better versus traditional technology would using this non-traditional technology (your answer from Question #8) make content delivery?

Back

Next

Technology and Higher Education: What Works and What is the Future?

Section 3: Technology in Higher Education: Content Practice

This section asks you to think about traditional versus non-traditional technology in CONTENT PRACTICE. Content Practice is how students personally engage with and experience the course content, and includes things like assignments, and classroom and outside of classroom exercises. Traditional technology is paper/pencil/computer-based tasks and overhead projection instructor-lead tasks. Any other technology used would be "non-traditional".

11. Please rate your agreement or disagreement with the following statement:

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Somewhat Agree	Neutral	Somewhat Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I believe courses where traditional technology (paper/pencil/computer-based tasks and overhead projection instructor-lead tasks) is used for more than 50% of the content practice will have a learning experience at least as good as courses where traditional technology is used for 50% or less of the content practice.	<input type="radio"/>						

12. Please rate your agreement or disagreement with the following statement:

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Somewhat Agree	Neutral	Somewhat Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I believe courses where non-traditional technology (anything OTHER than paper/pencil/computer-based tasks and overhead projection instructor-lead tasks) is used for more than 50% of the content practice will have a learning experience at least as good as courses where non-traditional technology is used for 50% or less of the content practice.	<input type="radio"/>						

13. What is the non-traditional technology that you are referring to in your answer to Question #12?

14. How should this non-traditional technology (your answer from Question #13) be used for content practice?

15. On a scale of 1-10, 10 being the most, how much better versus traditional technology would using this non-traditional technology (your answer from Question #13) make content practice?

Back

Next

Technology and Higher Education: What Works and What is the Future?

Section 4: Technology in Higher Education: Content Discussion

This section asks you to think about traditional versus non-traditional technology in CONTENT DISCUSSION. Content Discussion is the process of students asking questions, making comments, and getting answers about course content. Traditional technology is in-person classroom interaction with the instructor (hand-raising, etc.) and other students, email with the instructor and other students, and instructor-provided discussion boards. Any other technology used would be "non-traditional".

16. Please rate your agreement or disagreement with the following statement:

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Somewhat Agree	Neutral	Somewhat Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I believe courses where traditional technology (e.g., in-person classroom interaction with the instructor (hand-raising, etc.) and other students, email with the instructor and other students, and instructor-provided discussion boards) is used for more than 50% of the content discussion will have a learning experience at least as good as courses where traditional technology is used for 50% or less of the content discussion.	<input type="radio"/>						

17. Please rate your agreement or disagreement with the following statement:

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Somewhat Agree	Neutral	Somewhat Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I believe courses where non-traditional technology (anything OTHER than in-person classroom interaction with the instructor (hand-raising, etc.) and other students, email with the instructor and other students, and instructor-provided discussion boards) is used for more than 50% of the content discussion will have a learning experience at least as good as courses where non-traditional technology is used for 50% or less of the content discussion.	<input type="radio"/>						

18. What is the non-traditional technology that you are referring to in your answer to Question #17?

19. How should this non-traditional technology (your answer from Question #17) be used for content discussion?

20. On a scale of 1-10, 10 being the most, how much better versus traditional technology would using this non-traditional technology (your answer from Question #17) make content discussion?

Back

Next

Technology and Higher Education: What Works and What is the Future?

Section 5: Final Question

Thank you for participating in this survey!

21. Please rate your agreement or disagreement with the following statement:

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Somewhat Agree	Neutral	Somewhat Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I believe a fully online course provides a learning experience at least as good as a hybrid or fully face-to-face course.	<input type="radio"/>						

Back

Submit